

and increased productive tillers and IR50 grain yield (see table). There was little difference between carriers. Preemergence oxadiazon EC reduced early rice growth

but effectively controlled grasses, sedges, and aquatic weeds such as *Marsilea quadrifolia* and *Monochoria vaginalis*. It gave 4.7-5.9 t grain yield/ha compared with

3.7 t/ha for the unweeded plot. Mixing an EC formulation of preemergence herbicide with carriers, or direct sprinkling, is simple and economical. □

Rice field weeds of Mwea Irrigation Scheme, Kenya

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The Mwea Irrigation Scheme is the largest rice growing area in Kenya. It is near Mount Kenya, about 100 km north

Weeds of Mwea Irrigation Scheme, Kenya.^a

Weed species	Lifeform	Habitat
<i>Alternanthera sessilis</i> (L.) DC.	E	XO ●
<i>Ammannia auriculata</i> Willd.	E	XO
<i>A. baccifera</i> L.	E	X ●
<i>A. prieuriana</i> Guill & Perr.	E	XO ●
<i>Aponogeton absynicum</i> Hochst. ex A. Rich	FL	X ●
<i>Ceratophyllum demersum</i> L.	S	X ■ θ●
<i>Commelina benghalensis</i> L.	E	XO ▲ θ●
<i>Cyperus difformis</i> L.	E	XO θ●
<i>C. immensus</i> C. B. Clarke	E	XO θ●
<i>C. latifolius</i> Poir	E	XO θ●
<i>Diplachne caudata</i> K. Schum	E	XO θ●
<i>Echinochloa colona</i> (L.) Link	E	XO θ●
<i>Leersia hexandra</i> Sw.	E	XO ▲ θ●
<i>Lemna minor</i> L.	FF	X ●
<i>Ludwigia octovalvis</i> (Jacq.) Raven	E	XO ●
<i>L. prostrata</i> Roxb.	E	XO ●
<i>L. stolonifera</i> (Guill. & Perr.) Raven	E	XO ▲ θ●
<i>Mariscus assimilis</i> (Steud.) Podlech	E	XO θ●
<i>Marsilea macrocarpa</i> Presl.	FL	XO ▲ θ●
<i>Najas graminea</i> Del.	S	XI ■ θ●
<i>Nymphaea caerulea</i> Savign	FL	X θ●
<i>Ricciocarpus natans</i> (L.) Corda	FF	X
<i>Scirpus confusus</i> N. E. Brown	E	XO θ●
<i>Sesbania sesban</i> (L.) Merr	E	XO θ●
<i>Sphaeranthus bullatus</i> Mattf.	E	XO ●
<i>S. cyathuloides</i> O. Hoffm.	E	XO ●
<i>S. suaveolens</i> (Forsk.) DC.	E	XO ▲ θ●
<i>Typha angustifolia</i> L.	E	XO ■ θ●
<i>T. latifolia</i> L.	E	XO ■ θ●

^aE = emergent, FL = floating-leaved, S = submersed, FF = free-floating, X = inside rice crop, O = on levees of major canals, ■ = inside major canals, ▲ = inside major canals but floating, θ = inside feeder canal, ● = inside drains.

Frequency (%)

Distribution of weeds at Mwea Irrigation Scheme, Kenya, 1980-81 growing season.

of Nairobi. We identified the rice field weeds and examined their distribution.

Twenty-nine weeds were identified (see table). According to Sculthorpe's life-form categories, 22 were emergent, 3 floating-leaved, 2 submersed, and 2 free-floating. The major habitats of the weeds were within the rice crop, on the levees of major canals, and inside feeder canals and drains.

Weed distribution was studied in 1980-81 and percentage frequency was scored in 1000 1-m² quadrats. The figure shows the distribution has bimodal peaks

in Sep and Mar. The general decline in weed population between Sep and Dec might be attributed to weeding at the initial stages and drainage as the rice crop matures. The increase between Jan and Mar is due to reflooding and the subsequent reemergence of obligately aquatic weeds. Puddling and rototilling reduce weeds in Aug, when fields are prepared for the next season. The weeds could not be totally eradicated in Dec when dry-land conditions were prevalent because of the persistence of some weeds and nonuniform field preparation. □

Pest Control and Management

OTHER PESTS

Reaction of some upland rices to root-knot nematodes in rubber plantation fields

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In 1984, upland rice lines that were

grown and selected for intercropping in a pararubber crop at Kok-Primeng Rubber Experiment Station were seriously damaged by the root-knot nematode *Meloidogyne* spp. Infested plants had root galling, yellowed leaves and leaf sheaths, stunting, and low tillering. Based on the number of root galls, some lines had resistance to the nematode (see table). □

Field reaction of upland rice lines to root-knot nematode infestation at Kok-Primeng Rubber Experiment Station, Narathiwat, Thailand.

Cross	Selection no.	Infestation ^a (%)	Reaction ^b
SPR72103-67-2/IR208-78	SPRLR77205-3-2-1-4	37	MR
SPT7220-13-13-1/RD5	BKNLR77003-PSL-65021	81	S
RD11/IR28	SPRLR5010-149-1-1	92	S
RD1/IR28	SSPRLR75001-60-1-2	81	S
RD7/IET2845/IR4215-4-3-1-1	SPRLR223-53-2-2	87	S
IR36/RD25	BKNGB80076-5-08	25	R
IR36/RD25	BKNGB80076-6-030	31	MR
IR36/RD25	BKNGB80076-12-072	44	MR
IR36/RD25	BKNGB80076-15-050	25	R
IR36/RD25	BKNGB80076-17-091	31	MR
IR36/RD25	BKNGB80076-12-072	25	R

^a Av of 4 replications. ^b R = 0-25% root galls, MR = 26-50%, MS = 51-75%, and S = 76-100%.

The International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN) invites all scientists to contribute concise summaries of significant rice research for publication. Contributions should be limited to one or two pages and no more than two short tables, figures, or photographs. Contributions are subject to editing and abridgment to meet space limitations. Authors will be identified by name, title, and research organization.

Soil and Crop Management

Organic matter as a P source for azolla

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Azolla culture with lowland rice is drawing farmer interest in northeastern India. P is essential for rapid azolla growth, and P deficiency gives azolla a red-brown color. For best azolla growth, 8.8 kg P/ha must be applied, which is more than the total fertilizer applied by farmers in Assam. We studied organic matter supplements to provide P for azolla.

Cow dung and poultry litter, applied to equal 9 kg P/ha at 1- or 2-mo intervals were compared to 0 and 9 kg P applied at 1-mo intervals.

Results (see table) showed that azolla growth increased from Mar to May, then declined from Jun to Aug. In May, the interaction of application intervals and organic matter sources was significant. Azolla grew better with 2-mo applications of cow dung and poultry litter.

Results indicated that when organic matter is used as a P source it should be applied well ahead of azolla inoculation so soil microorganisms can break it down and make it available as an azolla nutrient. Applying 9 kg P/ha as single superphosphate significantly increased azolla production. □

Azolla biomass production as affected by P application and 2 application intervals of cow dung and poultry litter, Assam, India.

Organic matter source	Application intervals (mo)	P as SSP ^a (kg/ha)	Azolla biomass production (t/ha)							
			Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug
No organic matter	—	—	6.0	6.7	15.5	21.2	23.7	14.9	14.4	13.2
No organic matter	—	9	7.6	8.5	19.5	28.0	33.5	18.0	17.5	17.3
Cow dung	1	—	6.0	7.5	17.6	27.1	28.5	16.9	15.0	17.5
Cow dung	1	9	6.9	8.4	22.7	29.2	31.0	21.7	17.2	19.7
Poultry litter	1	—	5.6	8.1	16.6	23.7	24.0	18.4	17.2	20.7
Poultry litter	1	9	6.5	7.2	21.2	28.2	25.7	19.9	17.9	19.9
No organic matter	—	—	6.2	7.2	15.9	20.9	23.0	16.8	16.7	15.5
No organic matter	—	9	7.4	7.2	20.9	29.5	28.2	19.0	17.0	15.7
Cow dung	2	—	5.7	6.1	18.6	23.7	32.5	16.9	15.7	14.9
Cow dung	2	9	5.1	9.5	23.3	32.1	36.2	20.8	19.8	18.9
Poultrylitter	2	—	4.7	8.2	16.6	27.6	29.0	17.9	14.2	14.2
Poultrylitter	2	9	7.0	8.7	22.1	30.1	39.5	20.8	19.1	17.4
Mean	—	—	6.2	7.8	19.2	26.8	29.2	18.5	16.8	17.1
		SEm (P)	0.3	0.3	0.7	0.8	0.5	0.7	0.6	0.8
		CD (0.05)	0.8	ns	2.1	2.5	4.4	2.1	1.6	ns
		SEm (F × C)	0.4	0.6	1.3	1.5	2.6	1.3	1.0	1.5
		CD (0.05)	ns	ns	ns	ns	7.7	ns	ns	ns

^a Single super phosphate.

Nitrogen requirement and spacing for late-transplanted, photoperiod-sensitive, tall indica rice

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In parts of Bihar, early Jul floods wash out lowland rice. Farmers retransplant in Aug with old seedlings of tall,

photoperiod-sensitive indicas. Sometimes, labor shortages also delay transplanting. We sought to identify a suitable rate and time of N application and spacing for Janaki, a new photoperiod-sensitive variety suitable for poorly drained lowlands. A field trial was conducted at RAU Research Farm in 1981 kharif.

The experiment was in a split-plot design with three replications. Janaki was planted in four spacings and with six times and rates of N application (see